
A Study on Media use among Adolescents and Influences on Family Dynamics

Dr. Shalini Mathur

Associate Professor, Department of Home Science, Government Girls College Nathdwara, Rajsamand

Abstract Teenagers' lives have gotten more and more reliant on technology in recent years. The media is one factor that has been shown to have a significant impact on youngsters. The Internet, mobile phones, television, radio, newspapers, magazines, books, and broadcasting are all examples of mass media. Today's teens' lives are significantly influenced by the media. With all of this in mind, the current study's goals were to determine how the media affects adolescent family dynamics. The term "media" refers to any communication-related media technologies as well as the companies that own and manage them. Since the 1950s, the media film, radio, and television—have played a significant influence in determining political power in the nations that have attained a high degree of industrialisation. Through the information it disseminates and the interpretations it gives to that information, the media significantly influences how the public views a wide range of crucial problems. By choosing and presenting a specific set of beliefs, values, and traditions (a whole way of life), it also plays a significant role in influencing modern culture. In other words, by presenting a particular view of reality, it modifies reality so that it more closely resembles that interpretation.

Keywords Media, adolescents, technologies

Introduction

The media consists of the mobile phone, internet, television, radio, newspapers, magazines, books, broadcasting and text publishers. The Internet is significantly more influential than any other media. It is nearly twice as influential as TV and eight times more influential than traditional print media. The media is good for socializing and important in reporting people essential information and news, but it very often wastes people time and distracts their attention. All these manipulate adolescents in what concerns culture, politics, social life, religion, fashion, education and other interests. Almost each teenager has a TV in his room and he may stay stuck for hours in front of it to watch a show, a movie or to find out some interesting information on a discovery channel. The Internet has become much more important than the TV because it offers a range of facts on different areas of interest. Now adolescents prefer to download a movie from the Internet and watch it at home instead of going to the cinema as it is much more comfortable and at the same time, cheaper. Moreover, through e-mails they can communicate with adolescents in other countries and find other ways of thinking and behaving in society. Girls buy all types of magazines to find out some spicy facts about famous people and stars, while boys prefer magazines about cars or technology.

Advertisements and propaganda play a special role as they can influence young people to buy different things or to follow certain behaviours. Apart from this, media represents an essential source of enrichment and education for the young generation as they receive informal education from a variety of sources, from books to Internet. Media also

means entertainment, through music, sports, acting, video and computer games activities that help young people to escape routine and enjoy themselves.

Positive Effects of Electronic Media on Society

The media like television, radio and the Internet increase an overall awareness of the masses. They enhance the general knowledge by providing us with information from all over the world. News broadcast through different media helps us know about the day-to-day events in the world. News, telefilms and documentaries revolving around social issues increase a social awareness in children and develop their concern towards society. They also contribute to the enhancement of our knowledge, language and vocabulary. Quiz-based TV and radio shows, and the many programmes on history, literature, science, philosophy and art and culture on channels like Discovery, BBC and the National Geographic contribute to development of people's minds and attitudes, widening knowledge and culture.

Negative Effects of Electronic Media on Society

Media often hypes the basic facts or information and presents them so as to increase the superficial appeal of things. Media overemphasises on the money and 'glamour' aspects, film stars, models and the successful men and women in the fields of sports, business, art and politics. Television, magazines or the Internet, media is almost omnipresent, affecting various aspects of our life. The products advertised by the media, for instance, and the ways they are advertised are bound to affect the practices of the people. Television in particular has a major impact on the young, even toddlers, as it influences their viewing habits throughout their lives. Television violence is accompanied by vivid production features; children are predisposed to seek out and pay attention to sex and violence even in cartoons.

Adolescents and Media

Adolescents have a vast array of electronic tools for communication among them, instant messaging, mobile phones, and social networking sites. These tools are changing rapidly and are just as rapidly becoming independent of a particular hardware platform. Adolescents use these communication tools primarily to reinforce existing relationships, both friendships and romantic relationships, and to check out the potential of new entrants into their offline world but while the Internet allows teens to nourish existing friendships, it also expands their social networks to include strangers.

Among youth today, the popular communication forms include e-mail, instant messaging, text messaging, chat rooms, bulletin boards, blogs, social networking utilities such as Facebook and Whatsapp, video sharing such as YouTube, photo sharing such as Flickr, massively multiplayer online computer games such as World of War craft, and virtual worlds such as Second Life and Teen Second Life.

Objectives of the Study

- To find out the Personality traits in adolescent girls and boys.
- To find out the Interpersonal Relations in adolescent girls and boys.

Review of Literature

Kadiri K. K. and Muhammed A. Y. (2011) In the last 70 years, media such as radio, motion pictures, recorded music and television have become important agents of socialization. Media are important in socialization because they provide models of behaviour particularly among children. These models can have powerful effects on their behaviour, leading to behavioural problems. It is against this background that this study examines the relationship between media and children's behavioural problem in Kwara State of Nigeria in 2010.

Richards & Bursleson M. (2010) revealed that media has long been thought to have a detrimental effect on an adolescent's values and behaviours. Many social ills including violence, misogyny and negative health behaviours, as well as egoistic cultural values have been attributed to media's influence. Yet the media is not all powerful, nor

are its powers unable to be combated. In this manuscript, they analyze the Educational Longitudinal Study data from 2002 to 2006 to determine the real effects media has on adolescents in comparison to other influences.

Large (2005) notes, it is difficult to define categories such as children, adolescents, and young adults in concrete terms. National studies often define teenagers as between the ages of 12–17 (see Lenhart et al., 2010). However, Ito et al. (2009) observe that terms such as children, adolescents, and young adults are socially and culturally constructed labels. In their case studies of youth and media they define children as less than 13 years of age, teenagers and adolescents as between 13–18, and young adults as 19–30 years old.

Villani S. (2001) conduct a study, his objective was to review the research literature published within the past 10 years regarding the impact of media on children and adolescents. Media categories researched with computer technology included television and movies, rock music and music videos, advertising, video games, and computers and the Internet. Research prior to 1990 documented that children learn behaviours and have their value systems shaped by media.

Strasburg & Victor C. (1995) revealed that "Adolescents and the Media" provides a state-of-the-art review of research findings on the influence of such media as TV, movies, video games, print advertising, rock music, and music videos on adolescents. Beginning with a theoretical and conceptual background of adolescent development, the book covers findings on violence, sexual activity, substance abuse, and eating disorders, and makes a clear case that media play a distinct role in diverse facets of at-risk behaviour and adjustment.

Hansen F. & Nielsen C.J. (2004) described Danish 5-18 year olds children's situation in year 2000 based on TNS Gallup's quantitative annual children- and youth index. The focus is on the following topics: Children's economy and saving ability, children and the emerging electronic world, brand awareness, transaction knowledge and shopping, media use and, interest and activities.

Research Design

Research design is the plan, structure and strategy of investigation conceived so as to obtain the answers to research questions and to control variance. Research design refers to the overall strategy that we choose to integrate the different components of the study in a coherent and logical way, thereby, ensuring we will effectively address the research problem; it constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement and analysis of data.

Data Analysis

Table 1: Means and Standard Deviations of dimensions of Personality among Adolescent Girls and Boys

Gender	Openness		Conscientiousness		Agreeableness		Neuroticism		Extraversion	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
Girls	15.12	2.90	16.15	2.64	15.95	2.63	16.58	2.8	16.21	2.85
Boys	15.04	2.67	15.73	2.63	15.65	2.28	15.6	2.64	15.73	2.65

As can be seen from the table 1, adolescent girls are high on all the variables of Personality e.g. Openness, Conscientiousness, Agreeableness, Neuroticism, and Extraversion.

Conclusion

An interpersonal relationship is the nature of interaction that occurs between two or more people who interact and fulfil each other's explicit or implicit physical or emotional needs in some way. People in an interpersonal relationship may interact overtly, covertly, face-to-face or even anonymously. Your interpersonal relationships may occur with friends, family, co-workers, strangers, chat room participants, doctors or clients. An interpersonal relationship is a strong, deep, or close association or acquaintance between two or more people that may range in duration from brief to enduring. This association may be based on inference, love, solidarity, regular business interactions, or some other type of social commitment. Interpersonal relationships are formed in the context of social, cultural and other influences. The context can vary from family or kinship relations, friendship, marriage,

relations with associates, work, clubs, neighbourhood, and places of worship. They may be regulated by law, custom, or mutual agreement, and are the basis of social groups and society as a whole.

References

- [1]. Akman, I., & Mishra, A. (2010). Gender, age and income differences in internet usage among employees in organizations. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 26(3), 482-490.
- [2]. Amato, P. R., & Fowler, F. (2002). Parenting practices, child adjustment, and family diversity. *Journal of marriage and family*, 64(3), 703-716. DOI: 10.1111/j.1741-3737.2002.00703.x.
- [3]. Anderson, C. A., & Bushman, B. J. (2001). Effects of violent video games on aggressive behavior, aggressive cognition, aggressive affect, physiological arousal, and prosocial behavior: A meta-analytic review of the scientific literature. *Psychological science*, 12(5), 353-359.
- [4]. Baker, R. W., & Siryk, B. (1984). Measuring adjustment to college. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 31, 179-189
- [5]. Bell, R. Q., & Chapman, M. (1986). Child effects in studies using experimental or brief longitudinal approaches to socialization. *Developmental Psychology*, 22(5), 595.
- [6]. Bianchi, A., & Phillips, J. G. (2005). Psychological predictors of problem mobile phone use. *Cyber Psychology & Behavior*, 8 (1), 39-51.
- [7]. Cassell, J., Huffaker, D., Tversky, D., & Ferriman, K. (2006). The language of online leadership: Gender and youth engagement on the Internet. *Applied Developmental Psychology*, 42, 436-449
- [8]. Dresler-Hawke, E. and Mansvelt, J. (2008). Mobile phones: Enhancing social communication in young adult's lives? Massey University.
- [9]. Foreman, N., Boyd-Davis, S., Moar, M. (2008). Can virtual environments enhance the learning of historical chronology? *Instr Sci*; 36:155–173.
- [10]. Hampton, K., Wellman, B. (2001). Long distance community in the network society. *Am. Behav. Sci.* 45:476-95.
- [11]. Laughlin, Z. (2001). Mobile Phone Users: A Small-Scale Observational Study. Online Publications Sociology of the Mobile Phone, Social Research Institute, University of Zurich.
- [12]. Niaz, U. (2008). Addiction with Internet and Mobile: An overview. *Journal of Pakistan Psychiatric Society*, 5(2): 72.
- [13]. Palen, L., Salzman, M., Youngs, E. (2000). Going wireless: behavior & practice of new mobile phone users. CSCW_00, Philadelphia, PA. Parke, E. (2000). Make media maxims work for kids. *Education Digest*, 65, (6), 23-27

